

Shannon's Entropy and the Canonical Distribution

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Shannon's entropy emerges from the consideration of N independent trial runs with possible outcomes i with probabilities $p(i)$. For N large, one has $P(N \text{ runs}) = \text{product } p(i)^{N p(i)}$ or $\ln(P(N)) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } \exp(N p(i) \ln(p(i)))$. The quantity $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) \ln(p(i))$ is proportional to Shannon's entropy, thus as argued in (1), $\exp(-1/k \text{ Shannon's entropy})$ is the average probability for a run and so this factor multiplied N times gives the overall N trial probability. In other words, by knowing Shannon's entropy, one may calculate a pave and use this same probability for each of the N factors of $P(N)$ instead of having to know each $p(i)$ and $Np(i)$, the number of times they result.

We also noted in (1), that given any distribution of two variables $dy/dx=f(x)$, one may choose a region of x and create a kind of probability even if there is no stochasticity in the system. In this case, one introduces stochasticity through the measurement by sampling different x values using uniform probability. This approach is applied in the literature to the classical bound problem (see reference in (1)).

It is possible, however, that there exists stochasticity in a system as in the case of the toss of a coin, roll of a die or collisions in a gas. In the first two cases, one has independent events, but in the third case one does not because there is a constraint on the total energy of the gas. Nevertheless, one may try to approximate the collisions in a gas as being independent.

In the case of the coin or die there is no conservation of i , the variable associated with probability, but in the case of a gas, under the independent collision approximation, there is, namely energy of a single particle. Thus, not only is $\exp(-1/k S \text{ (Shannon)})$ the average probability for a single particle in N trial runs, but $S(\text{Shannon}) = E_{\text{average}} \text{ for a single particle} / T + \text{constant}$. Here T is a constant with energy units which may be fixed by calculating $E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{average}}$.

In other words, $P(N)$ is proportional to $\exp(-E_{\text{ave single particle}} N/T)$ which is the canonical distribution. As a result, the canonical distribution is linked to Shannon's entropy, but appears when one has conservation of the variable linked to probability.

Shannon's Entropy

$$\text{Shannon's entropy: } S = -k \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) \ln(p(i)) \quad ((1))$$

where i is an event and $p(i)$ its probability, seems to be linked to N trial runs (where N is very large) of independent stochastic events, like the toss of a coin or roll of a die, in the following way:

$$P(N) = \text{Product over } i \text{ } p(i)^{N p(i)} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Taking } \ln \text{ of } ((2)) \text{ yields: } \ln(P(N)) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(i) N \ln(p(i)) \quad ((3))$$

In the case of the roll of die or toss of a coin, i is not associated with a conserved quantity.

We also note, as pointed out in (1), that one may take a distribution $dy=f(x) dx$ and choose an x domain and create a kind of probability proportional to dy . Even if there is no stochasticity whatsoever linked with $y=f(x)$, one may treat this as a probability, but then the stochasticity becomes part of the measurement approach, i.e. one chooses x with uniform probability and makes a measurement of y . In such a case, one may mimic ((2)) and obtain a Shannon's entropy. This entropy, when used in:

$$\exp(-1/k \text{ Shannon's entropy}) \quad ((4))$$

represents the average probability for a dy/T detection if one makes a measurement at x . Here dx values are constant. An example is finding the entropy of a bound classical particle (see reference in (1)).

Thus, Shannon's entropy is used to find the average probability for a single event in a N independent trial run experiment so that one does not need to keep track of all of the i possible outcomes and their $p(i)$ probabilities. In other words, it tries to capture an average stochasticity.

The Case of a Conserved Quantity

We argue that the concept of Shannon's entropy becomes more interesting in the case of a conserved quantity. For the classical bound state, coin or die there is no conserved quantity, but for a Maxwell-Boltzmann, energy is the variable which stochastically changes and it is conserved. Thus:

$$p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_i+e_j) \text{ meaning that } p \text{ is a constant to the negative power of } e_i/T, \text{ where } T \text{ is constant with energy units.} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{One may use: } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((6))$$

In this case, $\exp(-1/k S(\text{Shannon single particle}))$ is the average probability for an independent energy state, but this becomes proportional to Eave single particle. Then:

$$P(N) = \{ \exp(-1/k S \text{ Shannon single event}) \}^{\text{power } N} \quad ((7))$$

((7)), however, is proportional to $\exp(-E_{\text{total}}/T)$ which is the canonical distribution weight.

Thus, the canonical distribution weight is the product of $N \exp(-e_i/T)$ probabilities or $(\text{pave})^{\text{power } N}$ where $\text{pave} = \exp(-1/k S \text{ shannon})$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Shannon's entropy is associated with N (N very large) trials of independent stochastic events with different probabilities. The idea seems to be that $(\exp(-1/k \text{ Shannon's entropy}))^{\text{power } N}$ represents $P(N)$, the probability for the N events. In other words,

Shannon's entropy is part of an expression characterizing an average even probability so that one does not need to keep track of all possible stochastic events and their probabilities.

We show that in the case of conservation of the stochastic variable: $P(e_i)P(e_j)=P(e_i+e_j)$ and one has $\exp(-e_i/T)$ as a solution for $p(e_i)$ unnormalized. The problem, of course, is that if e_i is conserved then there should be a finite amount of energy available and stochastic events would not really be independent, but it seems that for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one may approximate the situation as independent collisions. Then, Shannon's entropy becomes proportional to $1/T$ Eave per particle and $P(N) = \exp(-E_{ave}/T)$. This is the canonical distribution factor.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Meaning of Shannon's Entropy and Stochasticity of Measurement Versus System (preprint, zenodo, 2024)